

***Moringa oleifera* seeds for water clarification : A parametric study**

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Abstract : *Moringa oleifera* (MO) seeds have a remarkable affinity for removing impurities from contaminated water. The efficacy of MO seeds was ascertained from physical and bacteriological analyses. Subsequently, the results from these analyses were compared with the standards set by the American Public Health Association (APHA), American Water Works Association (AWWA), and Water Environment Federation (WEF). The effects of pH and temperature on the performance of MO seeds in the treatment of contaminated water were studied. The MO seeds were able to cause appreciable reduction in colour, turbidity, total coliforms, and faecal coliforms of approximately 97%, 93.75%, 85%, and 70%, respectively. Additionally, the MO seeds were able to achieve maximum turbidity reduction at an optimum pH of 7. Similarly, high temperature was found to increase the efficiency of MO seeds. Conclusively, conditions of contaminated water that fall within the ranges of the parameters studied makes MO seeds a promising candidate to augment the use of natural coagulants.

Keywords : *Moringa oleifera*, turbidity, alkalinity, TDS, coliforms.

Introduction

Clean water is the most important aspect for the well being of humans. Only 2.5% of the current water sources are fresh¹, and contaminated water can lead to the spread of infectious diseases that could affect the whole community^{2,3}. Water contamination may occur due to infected livestock, human wastes, and by other dangerous sources^{4,5}. Synthetic chemicals have some limitations, but are acceptable for water purification^{6,7}. Generally, indigenous and rural areas have improper water treatment systems, and they need practical systems to treat contaminated water⁸. Therefore, it is essential to use relatively simple and economical treatment technologies, such as coagulation⁹. Natural biodegradable materials can be used to purify turbid water in developing areas. Hence, the seeds of *Moringa oleifera* (MO) was recommended as a natural coagulant in water treatment in South Asia and Africa¹⁰. Meanwhile, polymers and inorganic coagulants are conventionally used to remove viruses, bacteria, and suspended solids from waste water¹¹. Meanwhile, ferric sulphate (Fe₂(SO₄)₃), and aluminium sulphate (Al₂(SO₄)₃) were mostly used for water treatment. However, these coagulants are relatively expensive and not readily avail-

able. Therefore, there is an urgent need to discover alternate options for water treatment in rural areas^{9,12}.

Conventional techniques, such as precipitation, membrane filtration, and ion exchange are often expensive, and produce waste by-products¹³. In contrast, coagulation can remove turbidity, and dissolves most chemical species in the precursor for water treatment^{14,15}. Chemical based coagulants, such as ferric chloride (FeCl₃), polyaluminium chloride (PAC), and alum are known for their effectiveness^{16,17}. Nevertheless, chemical coagulants have several disadvantages, such as ineffective performance under low water temperature, relatively expensive, have adverse effects on human health, can alter the pH of the treated water, and produce huge volumes of sludge¹⁸. Aluminium based coagulants can accumulate in human tissues, and can lead to Alzheimer's disease after prolonged exposure¹⁹. Therefore, it is necessary to replace chemical coagulants with naturally biodegradable ones to mitigate the previously mentioned problems. Several plants, such as *Jatropha curcas*, *Strychnos potatorum*, *Clidemia angustifolia*, and *Hibiscus sabdariffa* are used in developing countries to treat water. However, MO seeds were proven to be the more effective natural coagulant^{9,20}. Seed

proteins from MO are primarily responsible for water clarification^{21,22}. Approximately 37% of proteins were found in MO seed kernels²³. Coagulation is based on the neutralisation and adsorption mechanism. The coagulation process is more effective at pH of lower than 10 because positively charged MO seeds will seek out more negatively charged particles to bind and settle²³. They are exceptionally effective and non-toxic coagulants, and no dangerous symptoms have been reported by previous studies²⁴.

The purpose of the current study is to analyse the efficiency of MO seeds in water clarification process. The quality parameters of the treated water were tested after coagulation was performed. In addition, the effects of pH and temperature variation on the effectiveness of MO seeds were also investigated.

Methodology

Materials :

Raw water sample was collected from the Kerian River, which is located in Northern Perak, Malaysia. *Moringa oleifera* seeds were brought in from Aurangabad (MS), India. An ELE430-257 turbidity meter was used for turbidity measurements, and pH value was determined using a JENWAY 3505 pH meter.

Methods :

Colour, turbidity, alkalinity, total dissolved solids (TDS), pH, total coliforms, and faecal coliforms are the water quality parameters studied in this study. These parameters were estimated based on standard methods previously reported in the literature²⁵⁻²⁸.

Experimental

Sampling and handling :

Samples were collected and stored using standard methods to avoid alteration in water samples²⁹. Chemicals were used and preserved according to standard methods, and the samples were examined within 10 to 14 days after collection²⁹. The temperature, turbidity, and pH were measured quickly after sampling to avoid changes in characteristics and physical attributes.

Preparation of seeds :

Naturally dried seed pods were harvested from MO trees to be used in water treatment³⁰. The completely dried seeds were crushed, and sieved to obtain a fine powder. Different dosages of MO seeds were used, namely

50 mg, 100 mg, and 200 mg to determine the quality parameters of the contaminated water.

Coagulant preparation :

The normal sedimentation jar test was set up with two 1,000 mL jars, which were used with two samples simultaneously. Both jars have paddles that can be set at varying speeds, from 10 to 200 rpm. However, the paddles were set at a constant speed of 100 rpm during all processes. Then, different dosages of MO seeds were added into the water samples during agitation. Each mixture was rapidly stirred for 2–3 min, and then slowly for 12–15 min before being left undisturbed for 2 h. The resulting clean water was separated at the top of the beaker after sedimentation has occurred. The collected clean water was stored for further analysis.

Preparation of synthetic turbid water :

The reference stock suspension solution of 4,000 NTU was prepared as per the method prescribed in APHA-AWWA-WPCF (1980)³¹. The stock solution was then diluted further to obtain 80 NTU turbid solution, which was used to test the efficiency of MO with varying pH and temperatures.

Coagulation with varying pH and temperature :

Samples with varied pH values that ranged between pH 5 to pH 9 were prepared to investigate the effect of pH variation on the efficiency of MO. Hydrochloric acid (HCl), and sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were used to vary the pH of 80 NTU solution. The powdered MO seeds (500 mg) were added into the different pH samples. The mixtures were vigorously stirred using hot plate magnetic stirrers before they were allowed to settle for 30 min. Then, the resulting filtrate was used to estimate the efficiency of MO at varying pH.

Similarly, different water samples at 5 to 50 °C were prepared to determine the effectiveness of MO at varying temperature. Powdered MO seeds (500 mg) were added into each sample, and their temperatures were determined using a thermometer. A hot plate stirrer and a bathtub filled with ice were used to vary the temperature of the prepared 80 NTU solutions. The resulting mixture was filtered following a proper agitation, and was used for further analysis.

Results and discussion

The powdered MO seed was remarkable in terms of clarifying the turbid water sample. Table 1 shows the

Table 1. Effect of MO seeds on water clarification

Sr. No.	Parameter	Untreated sample	Treated with 50 mg MO	Treated with 100 mg MO	Treated with 200 mg MO	Std. limits (WHO)	Unit
Physico-chemical analysis							
1.	Colour	300	50	10	8	5 Max	Hazen
2.	Turbidity	80	30	15	5	5 Max	NTU
3.	Total Dissolved Solids	1148	99	724	623	500 Max	mg/L
4.	Alkalinity	600	404	455	455	200 Max	mg/L
5.	pH	8.6	8.0	7.5	7.3	6.5–8.5 Max	
Bacteriological analysis							
6.	Total coliforms	12	8.1	2	1.8	–	MPN/100 ml
	Fecal coliforms	6	1.8–70	< 1.8–70	< 1.8–70%	–	MPN/100 ml

effect of different MO seed dosage on various physico-chemical, and bacteriological properties of turbid water. The results were significantly better with higher dosages of MO seeds. However, the effect of lower dosages is not negligible.

Turbidity :

The turbidity of the water sample was at 80 NTU before flocculation was performed, which was higher than the standard limit of 5 NTU. However, this value gradually decreased with increasing dosages of MO, as shown in Fig. 1. The turbidity reductions were approximately 62.5%, 81.25%, and 93.75% with 50 mg, 100 mg, and 200 mg dosages of MO, respectively. The flocs settled more rapidly with higher dosages due to the increase in size. The coagulation mechanism of the MO seeds comprises of adsorption and neutralization of the colloidal positive charges that removes the negatively charged impurities from contaminated water³². The seed proteins of MO are an effective coagulant for water purification with 90–95% reduction in turbidity³³.

Fig. 1. Turbidity reduction at various dosages of MO seeds.

Alkalinity :

As shown in Fig. 2, the alkalinity of the turbid sample was recorded at 600 mg/L, which was reduced to 404 mg/L when treated with 50 mg of MO powder. However, the turbidity value was increased to 455 mg/L when treated with 100 mg, and 200 mg dosages of MO. The alkalinity reduction did not reach the desirable limit of 200 mg/L. However, this study has proven the alkalinity reduction capability of MO seeds. The precipitation of insoluble products may have caused the slight decrease in pH and alkalinity of turbid water sample. MO seeds have a natural capacity for buffering that can combine the light weight particles and form flocs, which settle more easily³⁴.

Fig. 2. Alkalinity reduction at various dosages of MO seeds.

Colour :

Fig. 3 shows the colour reduction of the turbid water sample following the coagulation process. The reduction was observed from 300 to 8 Hazen when treated with different dosages of MO seed powder. The colour removal efficiency was increased with increasing dosages

Fig. 3. Colour reduction at various dosages of MO seeds.

of MO due to the added available active components. Maximum efficiencies of 94% to 97% were recorded with 100 mg, and 200 mg dosages of MO seeds. These results clearly show the colour removal ability of MO seeds²².

pH determination :

The decrease in pH was observed with 50 mg, and 100 mg dosages of MO. However, pH was slightly increased with 200 mg dose of MO seeds, as shown in Fig. 4. The pH of the turbid sample was reduced from 8.6 to 7.3, which was within the desirable limit. pH reduction became higher with higher dosages of MO. The cationic proteins in the MO seeds are responsible for flocculation. The basic amino acids that are normally present in MO seeds can attract protons, and lead to a basic solution by releasing hydroxyl groups³⁴.

Fig. 4. pH variation at various dosages of MO seeds.

Total solids and TDS :

The Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) in the water sample was approximately 1,148 mg/L, which was nowhere near the desirable limit, as shown in Fig. 5. However, it was

Fig. 5. TDS reduction at various dosages of MO seeds.

reduced to approximately 15%, 37%, and 46% with 50 mg, 100 mg, and 200 mg dosages of MO seeds, respectively. The TDS reduction was not considered as excellent with only 200 mg of MO. Nonetheless, higher reduction can be expected with higher dosages of MO due to its chemical composition. It has basic polypeptides of different molecular weights, and each of them contains almost six amino acids, such as arginine, methionine, and glutamic acid²².

Bacteriological properties :

Fig. 6 shows that the total bacterial count for the untreated turbid water sample was 12.1 MPN/100 mL. This value was reduced to 8 MPN/100 mL, 2.1 MPN/100 mL, and 1.8 MPN/100 mL when treated with 50 mg, 100 mg, and 200 mg dosages of MO, respectively. A previous study has proven that MO seeds can act as an antimicrobial agent for pathogen removal³⁵. The 4 α -rhamnosyloxy benzyl isothiocyanate, also known as Glucosidal Mustard Oil (GMO), is an active microbial agent. The GMO can assist in the flocculation of solid matter, and removes a large portion of impurities, in terms of suspended bacteria³⁶.

Fig. 6. Pathogen removal at various dosages of MO seeds.

Table 2. Effect of pH and temperature variations on turbidity removal (MO: 500 mg/L)

No.	Untreated sample	pH 5	pH 7	pH 9	5 °C	30 °C	50 °C
1.	80 NTU	30 NTU	20 NTU	43 NTU	65 NTU	36 NTU	26 NTU

Subsequently, the faecal coliform reduction was more than 70% after the treatment. This result clearly shows the antimicrobial reduction potential of MO seeds. Contaminated water is unsafe for use because it can cause skin and gastrointestinal diseases. MO seeds are capable of producing antibiotic metabolites, such as 2,4-diacetylphloroglucinol and carboxylic acid, which can eliminate water-borne fungal pathogens^{37,38}.

Several studies explained that the chitinases and degrading enzymes can lead to antagonism that may result in the removal of fungal pathogens³⁹. The pathogen removal activity is directly proportional to the dosage of MO seeds powder^{40,41}.

Effect of pH and temperature variations :

The data for turbidity reduction with the addition of 500 mg/L of MO seeds is shown in Table 2. This table shows the effect of pH and temperature variations on the performance of MO seeds in water clarification. This study has confirmed that variations in pH and temperature can be effective in turbidity removal. The turbidity readings were gradually decreased when the pH was ranged between pH 5 to pH 7 but it increased again when the pH was from pH 7 up to pH 9. The decrease in turbidity was because at higher pH levels, the efficiency of MO becomes lower. Turbidity maximum reduction was at pH 7 with 75% of turbidity reduction. These results implied that the favourable range of pH was between pH 5 to pH 7 for turbidity reduction using MO seeds. Contaminated water has a similar range of pH in developing countries¹⁰; therefore, MO seeds can be a promising alternative coagulant to chemical coagulants. The U-shape in Fig. 7 is due to a decrease in zeta potentials. The zeta potentials can lower the flocculation ability of the sample at high pH level, as described in detail by Narasiah and Ndabigenesere²³.

Similarly, the effect of temperature on turbidity reduction was investigated. The findings favoured higher temperatures that can enhance the efficiency of MO seeds. Turbidity reductions were approximately 18.75%, 55%, and 67.5% at temperatures of 5 °C, 30 °C and 50 °C, respectively. These results show that higher temperatures

Fig. 7. Effect of pH and temperature variations on efficiency of MO seeds.

can lower the viscosity of the contaminated water, thus, improving the efficiency of MO seeds⁴². Additionally, lower efficiency can occur due to inter particle contacts, especially in water samples with low turbidity. Increasing the quantity of MO seeds can improve their effectiveness in low turbid water due to inter particle collisions. Normally, turbid water will have a temperature that ranges between 25 to 35 °C. This shows that the MO seeds can be an effective coagulant for water treatment in regions with similar temperature conditions.

Conclusions

The MO seeds have shown a remarkable coagulant tendency as well as being quite economic and safe. Therefore, MO seeds can be a promising alternative for water treatment, especially in developing countries. Excellent reductions were observed in turbidity, pH, colour, TDS, and alkalinity of the turbid water sample. In addition, MO seeds were found to be natural antimicrobial agents that can increase the reduction of microorganisms, and decrease the percentage of bacteria in water. The MO seeds also showed appreciable effectiveness at higher temperatures. This study has determined that the highest reduction in turbidity occurred at pH 7, which was the optimum pH level for applying MO seeds in water treatment. However, the accepted pH level was considered in between 5-7 because the turbidity reduction was not satisfactory at a pH higher than 7. This study has determined that MO seeds can be a promising alternative for water

purification in rural areas for sanitation schemes and community water treatments because they are eco-friendly, non-toxic, and a cheap source of coagulants.

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